

LARGE-SCALE MODELLING IN ANALYSIS OF STABILITY AND ISOLATED SOLUTIONS FOR NONLINEAR VIBRATIONS IN BLADED DISCS

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ABSTRACT

A methodology for the comprehensive frequency-domain analysis of stability of periodic vibration regimes of bladed discs with nonlinear contact interfaces is proposed. The methodology is aimed at using realistic finite models of bladed discs and other gas-turbine structures that can comprise very the large number of degrees of freedom. The methodology allows the assessment of stability of the nonlinear vibrations, calculation of the sensitivity of stability indicators to the design parameter variation and the determination of the domains of design parameter variation where the stability is achieved. The effective approach for the calculation of isolated nonlinear solution branches is also developed.

INTRODUCTION

Bladed discs and other gas-turbine engine structures are assembled structures with components interacting at contact interfaces. The interaction forces at these interfaces are nonlinear due to unilateral contacts, closing and opening gaps, friction forces, variable contact areas, cubic nonlinearities due to Hertzian contacts, etc.

In the majority of cases the steady-state periodic forced response is of major interest and the analysis of periodic vibration can be efficiently performed in frequency domain for realistic models of structures which customarily contain millions degrees of freedom.

The stability of the found nonlinear periodic vibration regimes is one of the most important characteristics that allows differentiating: (i) unstable vibrations – which are not practically achievable in usual operating conditions and (ii) stable vibration regimes – those that can be realised and maintained. The predictive analysis of the stability of nonlinear periodic vibrations has to be performed at the design stage and, therefore, represents an important practical problem.

The significant developments of methods for the stability analysis in frequency domain have been done relatively recently for systems although for rather restricted number of degrees of freedom (e.g. see Refs. [1]-

[5]) and for large-scale finite elements models (Ref.[6]). These methods allow the determination of the stability factors for any found periodic vibration regime. In Ref.[7] the method for analysis of sensitivity of the stability factors to contact interface parameters and design parameters of linear components of a structure was developed, which provide the useful information about how the small variations of design parameters can affect the stability of the vibrations

Moreover, the nonlinear vibrations have usually multitude of the solution trajectories. Frequently, the solution trajectories are not connected and cannot be traced by conventional solution continuation methods. These solution trajectories form isolated curves and their discovery, search and tracing requires development of special methods. This problem did not have a general solution so far, and the research in this area is still in a germinal state, although a few interesting papers considering systems with one or two DOFs should be mentioned here (see Refs.[8]-[11]).

In the proposed paper, the problem of analysis of stability of nonlinear periodic vibrations and isolated solution trajectories is formulated and solved in the frequency domain using the multiharmonic representation of periodic motion and high-fidelity models of nonlinear interactions at contact interfaces and large-scale finite element models of bladed disc components.

The multiharmonic equations are derived for: (i) the determination of the stability factors, (ii) their sensitivity to parameters of contact interfaces (gap values, normal loads, friction coefficient values, etc.) and (iii) determination of the boundaries of the stability domain with respect to design parameter variation.

An effective method for reduced modelling in the stability analysis is proposed. The method allows reduction of the large-scale models used for modelling of realistic bladed disc models by several orders of magnitude. The model reduction is performed as for the linear components of the assembly presented by large finite element models and as for large contact interface models describing multi-node contacts.

The solution of the frequency-domain stability equations is performed by Newton-Raphson method with continuation. The Jacobian and other derivatives of the equation solved are derived analytically, including the derivatives of the Floquet exponents with respect to multiharmonic vibration amplitudes, excitation frequency, aerodynamic damping, and contact interface parameters

TIME-DOMAIN EQUATIONS FOR NONLINEAR VIBRATIONS AND STABILITY

The equation for the forced vibrations of a structure with nonlinear interactions at joints can be written in the form:

$$\mathbf{K}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{x}} + \mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{x}} + \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \dot{\mathbf{x}}) = \mathbf{p}(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t)$ is a vector of displacements for all degrees of freedom in the structure considered; \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{M} are structural stiffness, damping and mass matrices of finite element (FE) model of a structure and $\mathbf{p}(t)$ is a vector of excitation forces; $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \dot{\mathbf{x}})$ is a vector of nonlinear contact interface forces which, for a case considered here, can be explicitly dependent on displacements, \mathbf{x} and velocities, $\dot{\mathbf{x}}$ of the structural components. The contact forces occur in gas-turbine structures at the blade root joints of bladed discs, at contact surfaces of underplatform or tip dampers, at contact surfaces of adjacent interlock shrouds and at rubbing contacts between rotor and casing. The causes of nonlinear behaviour are usually friction forces, unilateral interaction at the pairing contact surfaces, gaps, varying contact stiffness properties, as in the case of Hertzian contacts, etc. A case of periodic excitation forces is considered, $\mathbf{p}(t) = \mathbf{p}(t + 2\pi/\omega)$, where ω is the principal excitation frequency.

For any solution, \mathbf{x}^* , its stability can be determined by considering a perturbed motion $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}^* + e^{\lambda t} \mathbf{s}(t)$ and solving the eigenproblem obtained by linearization of Eq.(1) (see Ref.[6]):

$$\mathbf{M}(\lambda^2 \mathbf{s} + 2\lambda \dot{\mathbf{s}} + \ddot{\mathbf{s}}) + \left[\mathbf{C} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{x}}} \right] (\lambda \mathbf{s} + \dot{\mathbf{s}}) + \left[\mathbf{K} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right] \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{0} \quad (2)$$

The solution of this eigenproblem provides $2N$ eigenvalues $\{\lambda_j\}_1^{2N}$, where N is the total number of DOFs. The eigenvalues can be real or complex numbers, with the complex eigenvalues forming complex-conjugated pairs. The eigenvalue with the maximum real part defines the stability of the found solution: if $\lambda_{\text{Re}}^{\text{max}} = \max_{j=1..2N} \text{Re}(\lambda_j) > 0$, then the found motion is unstable.

FREQUENCY-DOMAIN EQUATIONS FOR NONLINEAR VIBRATIONS AND STABILITY

We consider the stability of periodic regimes, therefore, the equation of motion given by Eq.(1) and the stability equation, Eq. (2), can be formulated in the frequency-domain using multiharmonic representation of the displacements and the nonlinear forces.

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{X}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^{n_x} (\mathbf{X}_j^c \cos k_j^x \omega t + \mathbf{X}_j^s \sin k_j^x \omega t) = \mathbf{H}_x^T \mathbf{X} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{s}(t) = \mathbf{S}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^{n_s} (\mathbf{S}_j^c \cos k_j^s \omega t + \mathbf{S}_j^s \sin k_j^s \omega t) = \mathbf{H}_s^T \mathbf{S} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{X}_0, \mathbf{X}_1^c, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{n_x}^s\}^T$; and $\mathbf{S} = \{\mathbf{S}_0, \mathbf{S}_1^c, \dots, \mathbf{S}_{n_s}^s\}^T$ are vectors of harmonic coefficients for displacements, $\mathbf{x}(t)$, and for the periodic part of the perturbed motion, $\mathbf{s}(t)$, in the stability equation respectively and ω is the principal frequency of the periodic motion. It should be noticed that the total number of harmonics, n_x and n_s , and the harmonic numbers, k_j^x and k_j^s , used in the multiharmonic equations of motion and in the stability equation can be different. Their choice is determined by the accuracy required for two problems formulated here: (i) the analysis of nonlinear response amplitudes and (ii) the stability analysis of the found multiharmonic solutions.

The usual harmonic balance procedure applied to Eq.(1) provides the nonlinear equation of motion with respect to the vector of multiharmonic amplitudes, \mathbf{X} :

$$[\tilde{\mathbf{K}} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}\mathbf{E}_1 - \tilde{\mathbf{M}}\mathbf{E}_2] \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}) = \mathbf{P} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{F} = \{\mathbf{F}_0, \mathbf{F}_1^c, \dots, \mathbf{F}_{n_s}^s\}^T$; $\mathbf{P} = \{\mathbf{P}_0, \mathbf{P}_1^c, \dots, \mathbf{P}_{n_s}^s\}^T$ are vectors of nonlinear forces and excitation forces respectively and the size of matrices is increased by the factor corresponding to the total number of harmonics:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{M}} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{M}, \dots, \mathbf{M}); \quad \tilde{\mathbf{C}} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{C}, \dots, \mathbf{C});$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{K}, \dots, \mathbf{K}); \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_1 = \text{diag} \left(\mathbf{0}, k_1^x \omega \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ -\mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \dots, k_n^x \omega \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ -\mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_2 = \text{diag} \left(\mathbf{0}, (k_1^x \omega)^2 \mathbf{I}, (k_2^x \omega)^2 \mathbf{I}, \dots, (k_n^x \omega)^2 \mathbf{I} \right) \quad (8)$$

Here $\mathbf{I}(N \times N)$ is the identity matrix.

The application of the harmonic balance procedure to Eq.(2) gives the frequency-domain stability equation in the form:

$$[\lambda^2 \mathbf{I} + \lambda \mathbf{B}_1 + \mathbf{B}_0] \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{0} \quad (9)$$

This is a quadratic eigenproblem equation with respect to \mathbf{S} and λ , the matrices involved here have the following form:

$$\mathbf{B}_0 = \tilde{\mathbf{K}} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}\mathbf{E}_1 - \tilde{\mathbf{M}}\mathbf{E}_2 + \hat{\mathbf{K}}; \quad \mathbf{B}_1 = 2\tilde{\mathbf{M}}\mathbf{E}_1 + \tilde{\mathbf{C}} + \hat{\mathbf{C}} \quad (10)$$

The matrices corresponding to the nonlinear forces are indicated by a cap ‘^’ above the symbol and they are defined as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{K}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}}{\partial \mathbf{X}}; \quad \hat{\mathbf{C}} = \frac{2}{T} \int_0^T \mathbf{H}_s \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{x}}} \mathbf{H}_s^T dt. \quad (11)$$

The calculation of the vector of the nonlinear forced response, \mathbf{X} , and assessment of the stability of the found periodic vibration regime is performed by the solution of the nonlinear equation of motion, Eq.(5). Then the quadratic eigenvalue problem given by Eq.(9) is solved and analysis of all its complex eigenvalues is performed: in the case when one of them has a positive real part the vibration are unstable.

It should be noted that all matrices involved in the frequency-domain are obtained as a by-product of the Newton-Raphson solution of the nonlinear equation of motion given by Eq.(5): when the stability harmonics are included in the set of harmonics used for multiharmonic representation of nonlinear vibrations.

Applying the continuation techniques (e.g. arc-length continuation method) we calculate the dependency of the forced response multiharmonic amplitudes on this parameter. The choice of the continuation parameter can be done as it requires for the analysis. Usually the parameter can be chosen from three major groups of parameters: (i) parameters which describe linear components of the analyzed assembled structure, (such as natural frequencies, modal damping factors, material properties, parameters describing geometric shapes, etc.), (ii) parameters which describe the excitation loads (such as excitation frequency, loading levels and parameters characterizing distribution of the loads over a structure), and (iii) parameters of contact interfaces (such as contact stiffness, gap, friction coefficient values; level of static preloading at contact interfaces, etc.).

REDUCTION TECHNIQUES FOR HIGH-FIDELITY MODELS

The finite element models of gas-turbine engine structures and other critical machinery structures used by the industries contain very large number of degrees of freedom (DOFs) which customarily have $10^5 - 10^6$ DOFs. The multiharmonic representation of the solutions allows avoidance the unpractical search of the solution in time-domain - when the time-consuming integration of equation has to be performed. However, the size of the frequency-domain equations increases significantly. This requires the development the effective model reduction techniques for the high-fidelity analysis of vibrations and stability.

In order to perform the effective reduction of the multiharmonic nonlinear equation of motion given by Eq.(5) is transformed to the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R} &= \mathbf{X} - [\tilde{\mathbf{K}} + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}\mathbf{E}_1 - \tilde{\mathbf{M}}\mathbf{E}_2]^{-1} (\mathbf{P} - \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X})) = \\ &= \mathbf{X} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{P} - \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X})) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where the multiharmonic forced response function (FRF) matrix, $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, is expressed in the form through the FRF matrices of individual harmonics, $\mathbf{A}_{k_j^x}$:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \text{diag} \left(\mathbf{A}_0, \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{k_1^x}^{\text{Re}} & \mathbf{A}_{k_1^x}^{\text{Im}} \\ -\mathbf{A}_{k_1^x}^{\text{Im}} & \mathbf{A}_{k_1^x}^{\text{Re}} \end{bmatrix}, \dots, \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{k_n^x}^{\text{Re}} & \mathbf{A}_{k_n^x}^{\text{Im}} \\ -\mathbf{A}_{k_n^x}^{\text{Im}} & \mathbf{A}_{k_n^x}^{\text{Re}} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (13)$$

Owing to the fact that the number of nonlinear DOFs in contact problems is much smaller (sometimes by several orders of magnitude) than the total number of degrees of freedom, the reduction of the model is straightforward. It is done by the calculation of the high accuracy FRF matrices for each of the harmonics only for nonlinear DOFs as it is shown in Ref.[12]. As a result, the size of Eq.(12) is reduced to the number of harmonic coefficients for nonlinear DOFs only.

The multiharmonic stability equation described by Eq.(9) is reduced by expansion of the vectors of harmonic coefficients for the periodic part of the perturbed motion, \mathbf{S} , over mode shapes of the analyzed structure.

$$\mathbf{S} = \tilde{\Phi} \mathbf{c} \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{c} is vector of coefficients of the modal expansion; $\tilde{\Phi} = \text{diag}(\Phi, \Phi, \dots, \Phi)$ is the basis for the modal expansion.

Φ is a matrix of mass-normalised mode shapes of a linear structure calculated for a structure with the absence of the contact interactions by the solution of the following auxiliary eigenproblem:

$$\mathbf{K}\Phi = \mathbf{M}\Phi\Omega^2 \quad (15)$$

where $\Omega = \text{diag}(\omega_1^*, \omega_2^*, \dots, \omega_m^*)$ is the matrix consisting of natural frequencies, ω_j^* , corresponding to the mode shape vectors in Φ and m is the number of modes used in the modal expansion. Substituting Eq.(14) in Eqs.(9) and then projecting these equations on the modal reduction basis, $\tilde{\Phi}$, gives us the following reduced stability equations:

$$\lambda^2 \mathbf{c} + \lambda \mathbf{B}_1^r \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{B}_0^r \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{0} \quad (16)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B}_0^r = \tilde{\Omega}^2 + \tilde{\mathbf{C}}\mathbf{E}_1^r - \mathbf{E}_2^r + \tilde{\Phi}^T \hat{\mathbf{K}} \tilde{\Phi}; \mathbf{B}_1^r = 2\mathbf{E}_1^r + \tilde{\mathbf{C}} + \tilde{\Phi}^T \hat{\mathbf{C}} \tilde{\Phi} \quad (17)$$

$\tilde{\Omega} = \text{diag}(\Omega, \Omega, \dots, \Omega)$; and the expressions for matrices \mathbf{E}_1^r and \mathbf{E}_2^r are similar to those given in Eqs.(7) and (8), but the size of the identity matrix, \mathbf{I} , used in these expressions is reduced to $(m \times m)$.

The size of the stability equation is reduced to the product of the number of mode shapes used for stability reduction and the number of harmonic coefficients for one DOF. Since, as it is shown in Ref.[6], the number of mode shapes can be chosen small enough, then the full solution for the eigenvalue problem, Eq.(16) can be performed for realistic finite element models with large number of DOFs..

CALCULATION OF STABILITY BOUNDARIES

For the effective design, it is necessary to have a capability to determine a set of design parameters that can provide stable regimes of nonlinear vibrations. This can be done by formulating and solving a problem of determination of the stability boundaries: the design parameter values at which the vibration regime changes its status: from stable to unstable. In order to calculate the stability boundary we combine the both problems: (i) nonlinear forced response problem and (ii) the vibration stability problem in one equation:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{X} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\omega)(\mathbf{P} - \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}, b)) \\ \lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}(\mathbf{X}, b) \end{cases} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}, \omega, b) \\ \lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}(\mathbf{X}, \omega, b) \end{cases} = \mathbf{0} \quad (18)$$

where $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}$ is the real part of an eigenvalue which is obtained by selection from all eigenvalues of Eq.(16) the eigenvalue with maximum real part; b is the parameter which is analysed. The condition that $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}(\mathbf{X}, b) = 0$ is the condition that the design parameter value b is located at the stability boundary. The size of stability boundary

equation, Eq.(18) is increased by 1 comparing with the size of nonlinear equation of motion, Eq.(12), although for determination of $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}$ the complete eigenvalue problem has to be solved. The solution of Eq.(18) provides the nonlinear multiharmonic amplitudes of vibration at the stability boundary, $\mathbf{X}(b)$, and the excitation frequency value, ω , where the change of stability occurs. Both these characteristics are functions of a chosen design (or excitation) parameter, b .

Solution of this equation is performed by Newton-Raphson method and the extended Jacobian of this equation, required for the solution search with the parametric continuation, has the form:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\text{ext}} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial \mathbf{R} / \partial \mathbf{X}^n & \partial \mathbf{R} / \partial \omega & \partial \mathbf{R} / \partial b \\ \partial \lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}} / \partial \mathbf{X}^n & \partial \lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}} / \partial \omega & \partial \lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}} / \partial b \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

In order to ensure the accuracy, high speed of calculations and robustness of the process of solution, we derive the expressions for all components of this extended Jacobian analytically.

ANALYTICAL FORMULATION OF THE JACOBIAN FOR STABILITY BOUNDARY SEARCH

The analytical calculation of the first row of the extended Jacobian is generally known from the analysis of resonance amplitudes of the nonlinear forced response (see Ref.[13]). For a case when the design parameter is parameter of contact interfaces they can be expressed in the following form:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial \mathbf{X}^n} = \mathbf{I} + \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \hat{\mathbf{K}}; \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial \omega} = \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{A}}}{\partial \omega} (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{P}); \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial b} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}}{\partial b} \quad (20)$$

More general expressions can be found in Ref.[14].

In order to obtain the derivatives of the stability factor, $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}$, the right, \mathbf{c}_r , and left, \mathbf{c}_l , eigenvectors are calculated in addition to the corresponding eigenvalues. Then, the derivatives of the stability factors can be obtained by differentiating Eq.(16) and then multiplying from the left by \mathbf{c}_l^H . The resulting equation takes the form:

$$\frac{\partial \lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}}{\partial \gamma} = -\mathbf{c}_l^H \left[\lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}_1^r}{\partial \gamma} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}_0^r}{\partial \gamma} \right] \mathbf{c}_r / w \quad (21)$$

where $\gamma = \mathbf{X}, \omega, b$ - since we need the derivatives with respect to all these three parameters: harmonic coefficients of displacement, principal vibration frequency and the design parameter, moreover, $w = \mathbf{c}_l^H [2\lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}} \mathbf{I}^r + \mathbf{B}_1^r] \mathbf{c}_r$.

Taking derivatives of expression for \mathbf{B}_1^r and \mathbf{B}_0^r given by Eq.(17) we obtain the required derivatives of the eigenvalue.

- the derivative with respect to harmonic coefficients

$$\frac{\partial \lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}}{\partial \mathbf{X}} = \frac{\lambda}{w} (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_l)^H \frac{\partial (\hat{\mathbf{C}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_r)}{\partial \mathbf{X}} + \frac{1}{w} (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_l)^H \frac{\partial (\hat{\mathbf{K}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_r)}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \quad (22)$$

- the derivative with respect to the principal frequency of vibration

$$\frac{\partial \lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}}{\partial \omega} = \frac{1}{\omega w} \mathbf{c}_l^H \left[(\tilde{\mathbf{C}}^r + 2\lambda \mathbf{I}^r) \mathbf{E}_1^r - 2\mathbf{E}_2^r \right] \mathbf{c}_r + \frac{1}{w} (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_l)^H \left[\frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{K}}}{\partial \omega} + \lambda \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial \omega} \right] \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_r \quad (23)$$

- the derivative with respect to contact interface parameter

$$\frac{\partial \lambda_{\max}^{\text{Re}}}{\partial b} = \frac{1}{w} (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_l)^H \left(\lambda \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial b} + \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{K}}}{\partial b} \right) \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_r \quad (24)$$

The obtained analytically extended Jacobian allow highly accurate and robust solution of the nonlinear equation for the stability boundary determination, Eq.(18).

The multiharmonic contact interaction vector, \mathbf{F} , the contact stiffness matrices $\hat{\mathbf{K}} = \partial \mathbf{F} / \partial \mathbf{X}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{C}}$ and their derivatives: $\partial \mathbf{F} / \partial b$, $\partial \hat{\mathbf{K}} / \partial b$, $\partial \hat{\mathbf{C}} / \partial b$, $\partial \hat{\mathbf{K}} / \partial \omega$, $\partial \hat{\mathbf{C}} / \partial \omega$, $\partial (\hat{\mathbf{K}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_r) / \partial \mathbf{X}$ and $\partial (\hat{\mathbf{C}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \mathbf{c}_r) / \partial \mathbf{X}$ are calculated using the developed nonlinear contact elements for typical contact interface interaction: friction contacts, gap contacts, cubic nonlinear contacts, see e.g. Refs[16],[15]. These derivatives are derived analytically which again provides high accuracy of the calculation. These expressions are calculated for each of the multitude contact elements describing the contact interactions and then combined into the corresponding matrices for a whole structure using standard finite element procedure.

CALCULATION OF THE ISOLATED SOLUTION TRAJECTORIES

The robustness and efficiency of the developed method for the stability boundary calculation allows the use of the stability boundary calculation as a tool for search isolated solution branches – the problem which does not have a general solution so far. The search of the isolated branches is based on the fact that the stability boundaries in many cases are continuous over the whole manifold of solutions depending on the possible design parameter values. Because of this, the trajectory of solutions obtained by solving Eqs.(18) provides a solution which go through the stability loss points for all solution branches including the isolated branches.

It should be noticed that the determination of the isolated solution branches is of high practical importance since lack of the knowledge of the possibility of such solution can lead to missing dangerous operating regimes in gas-turbine engines. Some examples of the search for isolated solution branches are shown below.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The developed method for the parametric analysis of the stability boundaries has been introduced in an in-house FORTRAN computer code ContaDyn developed by the author. The capabilities of the method are demonstrated here on two models of structures with nonlinear contact interfaces: (i) a finite element model of a cantilever beam and (ii) a finite element of high-pressure turbine blade.

A cantilever beam

The cantilever beam considered has dimensions

1000×200×100mm and material properties are: elasticity modulus $E=10^5\text{N/mm}^2$; density $\rho=4.43\cdot 10^{-6}\text{kg/mm}^3$. 2 finite-element beam model is used – to be able to compare the results with results obtained in time-domain by direct integration of equations of motion. The case of viscous damping is considered and the modal damping factors of the beam are assumed 0.02 for all mode shapes. The nonlinear contact interface interaction is located at free end of the beam. The excitation force is applied also at the free end of the beam and the amplitude of the excitation force is 100N. The stability and forced response multiharmonic equations use first 10 harmonics: from 0 to 9.

For this model the gap nonlinear contact interface is considered when the nonlinear force function is assumed to be a function of the beam displacement, $x : f(x) = kx$ for $x \geq \text{gap}$ and $f(x) = 0$ for $x < \text{gap}$. In Fig. 1 the calculated dependencies are plotted as a function of the excitation frequency for different gap values. The contact stiffness of the gap nonlinearity is assumed: $k = 10^5$. For each calculated forced response curve stability analysis was performed and the stable parts of the forced response curve is plotted here and further in this paper in blue and the unstable parts are plotted by dotted red lines. The bold black curves show the results of the stability boundary calculations. The stability boundary curves go through the points on the forced response solution trajectories where the vibration regime changes its stability state.

Fig. 1 The forced response and stability boundary for different gap values

We can notice that for gap values 0.4, 0.3 0.1 and 0.005 the forced response solution trajectories have isolated branches of solutions, which have a closed curve shape distantly similar to a deformed ellipse. This isolated solution branches were found as a result of the stability boundary calculation which were calculated by changing the gap value. For the starting point of each stability boundary calculation a point on the forced response curve is chosen where the system changes its stability status. After the stability boundary curve is calculated, a point on this trajectory is selected. In order to calculate an isolated forced response curve such a point on stability boundary curve is selected where we still do not have a found solution point. Then this solution point is used as a starting

point for forced response calculation of the isolated branch.

It can be seen that for lower gap values (from 0 to 0.1) there are unstable parts for rather low vibration amplitudes: these unstable parts were unnoticed in previous studies of systems with gaps. The number of such parts and their length increases with the decrease of the gap value. In order to validate our stability calculations the time-domain equation of this system were integrated with slow variation of the excitation frequency in order to obtain time-domain solution close to steady-state vibrations. The time interval over which the equations of motion are integrated is 300 sec and a case of acceleration is considered here: when the excitation frequency is increased with the time. Because of the very large number of vibration cycles, the integrated vibration cycles are merged here in the blue area. The bold red line shows here the results of the multiharmonic frequency domain calculation and dotted parts correspond to unstable vibrations. One can see that the multiharmonic balance solution provides a perfect envelope for those parts of the solution trajectory where solutions are stable and for parts corresponding to unstable solutions the time-domain solution differ significantly from the periodic solutions calculated by the multiharmonic balance method. Moreover, we can see that the parts of the solution trajectory where the solutions are unstable were determined accurately.

Fig. 2. Time integration and MHB method for gap=0.025, time interval 300 sec

It important to notice the high practical importance of the calculation of the isolated branches. For the considered here case of gap value 0.05 the maximum possible amplitude of stable vibration on the isolated branch reaches 0.52 while the forced response curve calculated traditionally by tracing the solution from low to higher frequency values would produce much lower maximum amplitude value: 0.17. If we do not calculate the isolated branch, we do not know about the possible danger of higher vibration amplitudes. Although the major solution branches and isolated branches are not connected, a jump from one solution curve to another is possible under impacts or even sufficiently fast acceleration of an engine. To illustrate such a possibility a case of gap value 0.05 is

considered and the excitation frequency variation is performed fast enough to have some transient component in the forced response. In **Fig. 3** results of time-domain solution and multiharmonic balance solution for a case when the excitation frequency is varied over time interval 20 sec. For this case, the time-domain solution is still very close to the multiharmonic solution and it follows the major forced response curve. In **Fig. 4** results are shown for a case when the speed of frequency variation is doubled: the time interval over which this variation is performed is 10 sec. It is evident that vibration process jumps from the major frequency response curve to the isolated solution branch and, for this case, the vibration amplitudes reach much higher levels. In **Fig. 5** similar results are shown for a case of gap value 0.3, which has also an isolated branch, the transition from major response curve to the isolated branch is not achieved here.

Fig. 3. Time integration and MHB method, gap=0.05, time interval 20 sec

Fig. 4. Time integration and MHB method, gap=0.05, time interval 10 sec

The effect of gap stiffness value on the forced response and the stability boundaries for a case of gap value 0.05 is shown in **Fig. 6**. For a case of stiffness value $4 \cdot 10^5$ it is possible to find two isolated branches in addition to the major response curve. For each of the stiffness values $5 \cdot 10^4$ and 10^5 one isolated branch is found and for lower stiffness values isolated solution

branches are not found in the considered range of frequency and vibration amplitudes.

Fig. 5. Time integration and MHB method, gap=0.3, time interval 10 sec

Fig. 6 The forced response and stability boundary for different gap stiffness values, gap = 0.05

The isolated branches here were also searched using the stability boundary tracing method. One can observe here similar as in previously considered plots a multitude of unstable solution parts on the trajectory of solutions at low amplitude levels. These unstable solution trajectory parts occur when the stiffness value is high: in our case when $k \geq 3 \cdot 10^4$. The possibility of jumping from major response curves to the isolated branches was explored here also, but such effect was not found for the considered here cases.

An example of the comparison of the multiharmonic balance solution and the time-domain solution is shown in **Fig. 7**, where the time interval over which the frequency changes from 60 to 120Hz chosen rather small: 5sec, yet nor for the shown case nor for other excitation frequency acceleration rates the jump was not found.

The dependency of the stability boundary curve and the forced response on the contact stiffness value for a case of higher gap value 0.2 are shown in **Fig. 8**. For this case isolated branches were not found although the stability boundary curve indicates that such branches can be occur for high stiffness values.

Fig. 7. Time integration and MHB method, gap=0.05, $k = 4 \cdot 10^5$ time interval 5 sec

Fig. 8 The forced response and stability boundary for different gap stiffness values, gap =0.2

A high-pressure turbine blade

For the example of application of the developed stability loss boundary tracing method to a system with large number of DOFs, a turbine blade comprising 160,000 DOFs is considered. The blade finite element model is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. A cooled high-pressure turbine blade: a finite element model

The blade is fixed at the blade root contact patches

(marked in red in the figure) and the excitation forces are distributed over blade airfoil. The damping is chosen to be structural frequency-independent with all modal damping factors equal to 0.02. Two types of the nonlinear contact is studied: (i) cubic nonlinearity and (ii) gap nonlinearity. In both cases 12 nonlinear contact elements are distributed over a contact patch of the blade shroud (marked in yellow in the figure). In the multiharmonic forced response analysis all harmonics from 0 to 9 are used and in the reduced stability model 8 first blade modes are used.

The trajectory of stability loss points under variation of the stiffness for all cubic nonlinear contact elements is shown in Fig. 10 together with the results of forced response analyses performed for a set of different values (shown in the figure) of the cubic stiffness. One can see that the tracing method efficiently finds all stability loss points under continuous stiffness value variation. For this structure the isolated solution branches are found for the case of cubic nonlinearity: for $k = 3 \cdot 10^8$; $k = 4 \cdot 10^8$ and $k = 5 \cdot 10^8$. The isolated branches have not been found for smaller stiffness coefficient values, which can be attributed to the fact that the system becomes too weakly nonlinear for small cubic stiffness coefficient values to exhibit such vibration regimes. For higher stiffness value the isolated branches located possibly outside of the frequency range considered here.

Fig. 10 Forced response and the stability boundary for turbine blade: variation of cubic nonlinearity stiffness

Here again, the stability boundary tracing method finds stable high amplitude solutions which could be overlooked. For example, the analysis of the major solution branches shows here that the peak amplitude decreases by 60% when the spring stiffness increases from 10^8 to $5 \cdot 10^8$ yet, if we consider the found isolated branches, we can see that the maximum amplitude value is increased by 5% instead of the decrease.

The dependencies of the amplitude and frequency at the stability loss on the cubic nonlinearity stiffness value is calculated directly and for the turbine blade such is shown in **Fig. 11**. The complex character of these dependencies can be observed which can be captured accurately by the proposed method.

Fig. 11 The amplitude and frequency values at stability loss as a function of cubic stiffness for turbine blade

For the gap nonlinear contact interface, there are two parameters: the gap value and the stiffness value of the contact interface. For the results shown below these values are chosen to be the same for all 12 contact elements distributed over the blade contact interface.

The effect of variation of the gap value on the amplitudes of the nonlinear forced response and the stability boundary is shown in **Fig. 12** for a case when the stiffness value is 10^6 . It is interesting to notice the existence of isolated branches for higher gap values: $2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $4 \cdot 10^{-3}$, while for lower gap values two resonance peaks are observed. The forced response curves with isolated branches are plotted separately in **Fig. 13**. Here we can see that the isolated branches have trajectories of stable vibration regimes of substantial length and if, during engine operation, the vibration regime jumps to the isolated branch then the vibration amplitudes can have much higher amplitudes than predicted by major response curve. An example of the result of stability boundary calculation is shown in **Fig. 14** – the values of amplitude and vibration frequency are calculated directly as a function of gap value.

The effect of variation of stiffness value of the considered here gap nonlinearity on the forced response and stability boundary is shown in **Fig. 16**. For all curves plotted here the gap value is assumed 0.001. Isolated solutions are not found here, but for higher values (starting from $2 \cdot 10^5$) of the gap stiffness two resonance peaks are observed. Moreover, for stiffness values 10^7 and 10^8 we can see the beginning of forming of the isolated branches from the second resonance peak. The stable part of the solution trajectory at 2nd resonance peak is separated fully from the rest of the forced response solution trajectory by wide unstable parts and such regimes can be realised in practice under conditions similar to the conditions when

the isolated regimes occur. Nonlinear forced response curves are shown in **Fig. 16** for a case when gap value is fixed to 0.002 and gap stiffness coefficient is varied. Here we can see an isolated solution branch for the stiffness value 10^6 and almost isolated branch for stiffness value 10^8 .

Fig. 12 Forced response and the stability boundary for turbine blade: the variation of gap value

Fig. 13 Forced response of the turbine blade with found isolated branches

Fig. 14 The amplitude and frequency values at stability loss as a function of gap value for turbine blade

Fig. 15 Forced response and the stability boundary: the variation of stiffness value (gap = 0.001)

Fig. 16 Forced response and the stability boundary: the variation of stiffness value (gap = 0.002)

CONCLUSIONS

A methodology for analysis of the stability of the nonlinear forced response and the boundaries of the dynamic stability has been developed.

The methodology allows the analysis of industrial-size finite element models of bladed disks and other critical structures with contact interfaces

The methods developed allow parametric analysis of the stability loss points determining design parameter values corresponding to the stability boundaries together with the vibration amplitudes and vibration at the stability boundary.

The method uses the multiharmonic representation of the periodic forced response and effective model reduction techniques aimed at the analysis of realistic gas-turbine structures comprising thousands and millions degrees of freedom.

The method provides an effective tool for the search of isolated branches of the nonlinear solutions. Examples of detection and search of the isolated branches are given: for relatively small and for large-scale finite element models.

The scenarios of realization of the vibration on the isolated solution branches are discussed and examples of such scenarios are provided.

The efficiency of the methodology is demonstrated on simple systems and on a large-scale model of a turbine blade.

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